

Spectrophotometric studies on the charge-transfer complexes between tetryl with amines in DMSO and determination of the vertical electron affinity of tetryl

S. P. Sharma^a and S. C. Lahiri*

Central Forensic Science Laboratory, 30, Gorachand Road, Kolkata-700 014, India

E-mail : sprasadsharma@rediffmail.com, sujitclahiri@yahoo.com

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Abstract : Tetryl (*N*-2,4,6-tetranitro-*N*-methylaniline) formed beautifully colored complexes with aliphatic amines like isopropylamine, ethylenediamine, tetraethylenepentamine and bis(3-aminopropyl)amine acting as chromogenic agents in DMSO having two distinct peaks near 447 nm and 517 nm respectively. The complexes were stable for 12 h. The extinction coefficients (fairly high) of the amino complexes of tetryl were determined directly by using the concentration of amines 400 times more than that of tetryl. The complexes were observed to be 1 : 1 type using Job's method of continuous variations. The thermodynamic association constants of the complexes were determined directly using the extinction coefficient values at 298 K at two wavelengths. The results agreed well. The results were also verified by calculating K_{DA} using the iteration method. The energies of transition for the CT complexes $h\nu_{CT}$ found experimentally agreed reasonably well with the theoretical energies of CT transitions (from HOMO to donor and LUMO to acceptor) obtained using DFT calculations. The vertical electron affinity E_A^V of tetryl was calculated using the method suggested by Mulliken. However, FTIR measurements of the tetryl complexes could not be performed due to experimental and technical limitations.

Keywords : Association constants (K_{DA}), CT complexes, DMSO, spectrophotometry, vertical electron affinity.

Introduction

Charge-transfer (CT) or EDA (electron donor acceptor) interactions in understanding biological process and in understanding the role of weak interactions in drug-receptor interactions have been studied extensively¹⁻¹². Charge transfer complex formation is also the basis of identification and quantification of many explosives^{2,13}. The utilization of charge-transfer complex formation between a large number of nitro explosives like TNT and nitromusks with 3,3-iminobispropylamine for the detection of explosives was reported by Douse and co-workers^{14,15}. Dwivedy *et al.*¹⁶ also reported CT complexes with TNT and *m*-dinitrobenzene with aromatic amines in non-polar solvents. Urbanski¹³ reported the formation of CT complexes between nitro compounds and amines. But in most of these cases, no attempt was made to study the association constants K_{DA} and other properties of the complexes. In recent papers, Sharma and Lahiri¹⁰ reported the absorption, the association constants of the CT complexes, the spectroscopic and FTIR studies on EDA com-

plexes between DNB (dinitro benzene) and TNT (2,4,6-trinitrotoluene) with amines in DMSO. They also determined the vertical electron affinities of DNB and TNT and other aspects using AMI and DFT calculations¹⁷. The quantification of TNT based on CT complex formation was also reported but such attempt to quantify DNB using CT complex formation failed. Tetryl (*N*-2,4,6-tetranitro-*N*-methylaniline) is powerful explosive, widely used for mortars, bombs, detonators¹³ and is similar to TNT but -CH₃ group of TNT is replaced by $\text{—N} \begin{matrix} \text{NO}_2 \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{matrix}$ group. It is expected that tetryl like TNT will form CT complexes with amines. Raha *et al.*¹⁸ reported spectroscopic studies on EDA complex between tetryl and ethylenediamine in acetonitrile. However, the complex formation with other amines were not reported by them. Therefore, it is desirable to study the association constants and properties of the tetryl + amines [isopropylamine (IPA), ethylenediamine (EDA), bis(3-aminopropyl)amine (BAPA), tetraethylenepentamine (TEPA)] in DMSO. However, no

^aPresent address : Geological Survey of India, Eastern Region, DK-6, Sector-II, Salt Lake City, Kolkata-700 091, India.

thermodynamic properties and FTIR studies were made due to experimental limitations. The correlation of the experimental CT energies with theoretical energy values using DFT¹⁷ calculation was made. The results of our investigations are presented in this article.

Experimental

Tetryl (standard sample was taken from High Energy Material Research Laboratory, Pune) was used as such. Isopropylamine, ethylenediamine, bis(3-aminopropylamine), tetraethylenepentamine used were of G.R. quality from Fluka, Switzerland. DMSO and other solvents used were of HPLC grade (Spectrochem India Pvt. Ltd.). The ligands do not absorb in the UV and visible region but tetryl absorbs in the UV region. Tetryl forms beautifully colored complexes with amines mentioned above with two distinct peaks (Fig. 1) unlike TNT which gave three distinct peaks. The results are summarized in Table 1.

The compositions of the complexes were determined using Job's method of continuous variation taking equimolar solution of tetryl and amines (concentration 1×10^{-5} M) in DMSO. The optical density measurements were

Fig. 1. The UV-Visible spectrum of tetryl and amine complex.

taken at the desired wavelengths of absorption maxima of the respective complexes near 447 nm and 517 nm.

The direct determination of extinction coefficients of the complexes is always desirable if possible. In the present experiment, it was observed that the o.d of the solutions containing tetryl increased with increasing concentrations of the amines and became constant in presence of large excess of amines. It had been observed that about 400 times or more of amines were required for the complete conversion of tetryl into complexes. The complexes were stable for 12 h. From the optical densities of totally complexed tetryl, extinction coefficients of the complexes were determined (Table 2).

For the determination of the association constants, different solutions of tetryl and amines were prepared almost in stoichiometric ratios and optical density measurements were made at the desired wavelengths at 298 K. The measurements were made after 1 h. Preparation of solid amine complex of tetryl was not possible due to technical reasons as amines react with many organic solvents. However, due to volatile nature of amines, extraction of complexes by evaporation of solvents led to the decomposition of the complexes and the measurement of FTIR spectra of the complexes in DMSO solution could not be done due to technical limitations.

Results

The complex formations between tetryl and amines were found to be 1 : 1 from Job's method of continuous variations. The association constant K for the 1 : 1 complex

$D + A \rightleftharpoons DA$ (D = amines and A = m -DNB) can be written as

$$K = \frac{[DA]}{[D][A]} \times \frac{\gamma[DA]}{\gamma[D] \times \gamma[A]} \approx \frac{[DA]}{[D][A]} \quad (1)$$

Table 1. Thermodynamic association constants of the complexes of tetryl and amines were determined directly using the extinction coefficient values and iteration method at 298 K at two wavelengths

Sl. no.	Reagents	Absorption bands (nm)	K at 447 nm	K at 447 nm iteration	K at 517 nm	K at 517 nm iteration
1.	Tetryl + IPA	446, 517	5.73×10^3	5.23×10^3	5.68×10^3	5.11×10^3
2.	Tetryl + EDA	447, 516	1.71×10^4	1.32×10^4	1.48×10^4	1.67×10^4
3.	Tetryl + BAPA	449, 519	1.21×10^5	1.34×10^5	1.34×10^5	1.45×10^5
4.	Tetryl + TEPA	448, 519	2.61×10^4	2.50×10^4	2.72×10^4	2.19×10^4

$$\text{[assuming, } \frac{\gamma[\text{DA}]}{\gamma\text{D} \cdot \gamma[\text{A}]} = 1]$$

$$\text{Thus, } K = \frac{x}{(c_1-x)(c_2-x)} \quad (2)$$

where c_1 and c_2 were the initial concentrations of D and A and x was the concentration of the complex at equilibrium respectively. x was determined directly from the o.d values of the experimental solutions and extinction coefficients of the complexes determined previously from which the association constants of the complex were calculated using eq. (2). The experiment was done at two different wavelengths for each of the complexes. The association constants of the complexes and their extinction coefficient values are recorded in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

In many cases, the compositions of the CT or EDA complexes could not be determined and the association constants K_{DA} were obtained using Benesi-Hildebrand equation using $D \gg A$ or $A \gg D$ ($D = \text{donor}$, $A = \text{acceptor}$), which however, cannot give accurate values of the association constants. Moreover, in the iterative ex-

trapolations, the intercept and slope give $\frac{1}{\epsilon}$ and $\frac{1}{K_{\text{DA}} \cdot \epsilon}$.

Even if accurate values of $\frac{1}{K_{\text{DA}} \cdot \epsilon}$ are obtained from the

slopes but there are considerable uncertainty in $\frac{1}{\epsilon}$, which

leads to relatively uncertain K_{DA} values. In general, direct determination of extinction coefficients of the CT complexes is not possible but the extinction coefficients of TNT + amine and tetryl + amine complexes were determined directly.

Table 2. The extinction coefficient of the complexes of tetryl and amines at 298 K at different wavelengths

Tetryl	Isopropylamine	Absorbance at 447 nm	Absorbance at 517 nm	Extinction coefficient of the complex at 447 nm	Extinction coefficient of the complex at 517 nm
1×10^{-5}	1×10^{-3}	0.1299	0.1302	1.299×10^4	1.302×10^4
	4×10^{-3}	0.1390	0.1311	1.390×10^4	1.311×10^4
	5×10^{-3}	0.1391	0.1314	1.391×10^4	1.314×10^4
	6×10^{-3}	0.1396	0.1312	1.396×10^4	1.312×10^4
	7×10^{-3}	0.1390	0.1311	1.390×10^4	1.311×10^4
	8×10^{-3}	0.1392	0.1313	1.392×10^4	1.313×10^4
	1×10^{-2}	0.1391	0.1313	1.391×10^4	1.313×10^4
Tetryl 1×10^{-5}	Bis(3-aminopropyl)amine				
	1×10^{-3}	0.1990	0.1285	1.990×10^4	1.285×10^4
	4×10^{-3}	0.2229	0.1460	2.229×10^4	1.460×10^4
	5×10^{-3}	0.2249	0.1472	2.249×10^4	1.472×10^4
	6×10^{-3}	0.2250	0.1479	2.250×10^4	1.479×10^4
	7×10^{-3}	0.2249	0.1474	2.249×10^4	1.474×10^4
	8×10^{-3}	0.2248	0.1479	2.248×10^4	1.479×10^4
1×10^{-2}	0.2251	0.1473	2.251×10^4	1.473×10^4	
Tetryl 1×10^{-5}	Tetraethylenepentamine				
	1×10^{-3}	0.2088	0.1351	2.088×10^4	1.351×10^4
	4×10^{-3}	0.2346	0.1451	2.346×10^4	1.451×10^4
	5×10^{-3}	0.2344	0.1456	2.344×10^4	1.456×10^4
	6×10^{-3}	0.2351	0.1448	2.351×10^4	1.448×10^4
	7×10^{-3}	0.2348	0.1452	2.348×10^4	1.452×10^4
	8×10^{-3}	0.2345	0.1457	2.345×10^4	1.457×10^4
1×10^{-2}	0.2346	0.1454	2.346×10^4	1.454×10^4	

Tetryl	Ethylenediamine				
1×10^{-5}	1×10^{-3}	0.2471	0.1440	2.471×10^4	1.440×10^4
	4×10^{-3}	0.2510	0.1525	2.510×10^4	1.525×10^4
	5×10^{-3}	0.2510	0.1523	2.510×10^4	1.523×10^4
	6×10^{-3}	0.2506	0.1527	2.506×10^4	1.527×10^4
	7×10^{-3}	0.2511	0.1526	2.511×10^4	1.526×10^4
	8×10^{-3}	0.2510	0.1522	2.510×10^4	1.522×10^4
	1×10^{-2}	0.2508	0.1525	2.508×10^4	1.525×10^4

Fig. 2. Calculation of adiabatic electron affinity of tetryl.

For comparison the association constants of the complexes were also determined indirectly using the usual iterative procedure. The general formula for the determination of ϵ (extinction coefficient of the complex) and association constant $K^{5,12}$ is

$$\frac{c_1}{d-d_1-d_2} = \frac{1}{\epsilon-\epsilon_1-\epsilon_2} + \frac{1}{Kc_{1-x} \epsilon-\epsilon_1-\epsilon_2 l} \quad (3)$$

when the complex and the components absorb in the same region or at the wavelength under study.

But in the present experiment, only the complex absorbed at the wavelength under study, the equation reduces to

$$\frac{c_1}{d} = \frac{1}{\epsilon l} + \frac{1}{K(c_{1-x})\epsilon l} \quad (4)$$

where d and ϵ represented the optical densities of the experimental solutions and extinction coefficient of the complex. The eq. (4) is akin to Benesi-Hildebrand (B-H) equation¹⁹ but the experimental conditions were different. It had been observed that tetryl was completely complexed with amine concentrations nearly 400 times more than that of tetryl. Naturally, the condition $D \gg A$ required for B-H equation, could not be maintained. But the eq. (4) can be utilized even if D and A are in stoichiometric ratios.

It has been found experimentally, K_{DA} values for reaction of the type (1) calculated under conditions $D \gg A$ and $D = A$ differ considerably^{8,9,12}. Comparison of the results of K_{DA} of complexes obtained from the determination under various conditions and using different methods led Foster² to suggest that more weight should be given to values where $[D] = [A]$. Job's method of continuous variations exactly emphasize that absorption maximum or minimum (depending on the absorptivity of the complex) occurs when D and A are in stoichiometric ratios. Other limitations of B-H equation were outlined before⁸⁻¹².

Discussion

From ϵ and d values of the complexes in solution, x , i.e. the equilibrium concentrations of the complexes in solution were determined directly and K_{DA} values of the complexes were determined using eq. (2). The results are presented in Table 1. However, K_{DA} and ϵ values were also determined from eq. (4) using the process of iteration taking $x = 0$ initially⁵⁻¹². The results are also presented in Tables 1 within parenthesis.

Both $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions are possible for tetryl like TNT. The spectral solvent shifts of tetryl could not be studied from the absorption measurements of tetryl in methanol, acetone, chloroform and DMSO as most of the solvents have cut off points above 230 nm or more and the absorption maximum of tetryl is in the region 230 nm.

It has been previously reported, amines interact with solvents like methanol, ethanol, acetone, acetonitrile, dioxane etc. and the complex formation of amines and tetryl are observed only with large excess of amines. However, DMSO was found to be an ideal solvent for the study of the complexes and the complexes were formed when tetryl and amines were in stoichiometric ratios.

Tetryl when added to amine form colored complexes with two conspicuous peaks near 447 nm and 517 nm. The spectra of the complexes are given in Fig. 1 and the wavelengths of absorption maxima are given in Table 1.

It is to be noted that TNT gives three peaks with isopropylamine whereas other amines give four peaks with TNT. The peaks are in the region 370–380 nm, 463 nm (for higher amines), 532 nm and 629 nm. The peak near 463 nm vanished rapidly.

Raha *et al.*¹⁸ made spectroscopic studies on EDA complexes between tetryl and ethylenediamine in acetonitrile, methanol and ethanol. They considered the formation of two charge-transfer complexes having 1 : 1 ratio of donor to acceptor with absorption maxima at 440 nm and 340 nm respectively. They suggested that the initial complex ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 440$ nm) was converted to a product complex ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 340$ nm) in solution following first order kinetics when EDA concentration was lowered. They reported the isolation of the product complex (not the complex at 440 nm) and their characterization.

However, in our experiment, only two distinct bands were observed and peaks for the complexes with absorption maxima at 447 nm and 517 nm in DMSO solution with all the amines but the band at 340 nm is conspicuously absent.

The compositions of the complexes were found to be 1 : 1 in all cases by Job's method of continuous variation and from measurements at both the wavelengths. The association constants of the tetryl + amine complexes (Table 1) were also found to be the same at both wavelengths. The complexes are fairly stable but less stable than TNT + amine complexes. Thus, only one complex was formed in solutions. This is true for all the measurements. The complexes are of $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ type.

The association constants of the tetryl complexes are almost similar with little variations. The order of the association constants of tetryl with amines are in the order : EDA complex > bis(3-aminopropyl)amine complex > tetraethylenepentamine complex > isopropylamine complex. It is seen that in case of TNT + ethylenediamine (or other diamine or higher amine) complex, the transient band near 463–470 nm becomes prominent with time. Thus, the complexes reported by Raha *et al.*¹⁸ may be due to TNT (present as impurity in tetryl) or other decomposition products of tetryl as impurities in tetryl.

Urbanski¹³ reported blood red colored complexes of TNT with absorption maxima at 460 nm and 540 nm using Janovsky's²⁰ reaction (adding 30% NaOH or KOH in TNT in acetone or alcohol) but no such complex formation was reported for tetryl.

No study on the thermodynamics of complexes was made but the results suggest an ordered system with decrease in the number of molecules with loss of the degrees of freedom due to association. There is possibility of solvational or conformational changes due to association, but it was not possible to throw light regarding solvational or conformational changes though (ΔG°) changes involve both. Moreover, contributions due to dipole-dipole, dipole-induced dipole and other dispersion effects to the ground state stabilization of the complexes may be considerable.

Evidence of charge-transfer complex formation and the determination of the vertical electron affinity (E_A^V) of tetryl (the acceptor) :

There may be some controversy as to the nature of the CT complexes in spite of stable color of the complexes. Aromatic nitro compounds particularly with two or more nitro groups react with bases (nucleophilic reactions) and the reactions are usually associated with the formation of intense colors known as Janovsky reaction^{13,20}. The reaction occurs when nitro compounds in acetone or alcohol are treated with concentrated 30% solution of NaOH or KOH.

The mechanism of the Janovsky reaction, however, is not understood properly. In the present study, absorption maxima were in the region 447–517 nm and the reaction conditions were different. Moreover, the plots of $h\nu_{\text{CT}}$ (transition energy) of the complexes against I.P (vertical ionization potential of amines obtained using DFT¹⁷) showed a linear relationship in accordance to Mc Connell-Ham-Platt equation²¹.

$$h\nu_{\text{CT}} = I_{\text{D}}^{\text{V}} - E_{\text{A}}^{\text{V}} - W \quad (5)$$

where W is the dissociation energy of the charge-transfer complex in the excited state. The results suggested that the complexes were charge-transfer complexes without doubt. I_{D} and E_{A} of donors and acceptors were calculated using DFT calculations [using B3LYP method with basis set 6-311+G (d,p)]. The true values of ionization energies, however, are I_{D}^{Ad} and E_{A}^{Ad} i.e. adiabatic ion-

ization and electron affinity energy values. I_D^{Ad} and E_A^{Ad} are the energies involved in the transition of electrons from the outermost orbital (HOMO) to infinity or from infinity to HOMO or LUMO. The true energy values can be obtained using photoionization coupled with mass-spectrometry methods but these are not available. However, I_D^{Ad} and E_A^{Ad} values were calculated from the energy differences of (i) D and D^+ and (ii) A and A^- using DFT. The adiabatic and vertical energy values (I_D^{Ad} and E_A^{Ad}) and (I_D^V and E_D^V) using the method of Mulliken^{22,23} and Koopman²⁴ are presented in Table 3. The Table 3 also contain a comparison of theoretical and experimental E_A^V values obtained from different I_D values.

The theoretical equations

$$h\nu_{CT} = I_D^V - c_1 + \frac{c_2}{I_D^V - C_1} \quad (6)$$

suggested by Mulliken^{2,22,23} was used for the calculation of I_D^V .

Here

$$C_1 = E_A^V + G_1 + G_0 \quad (7)$$

G_0 is the binding energy of no-bond function and the binding is due to physical forces like dipole-dipole, dipole-induced dipole interactions, London dispersion forces

Table 3A. Comparison of electron affinity values of tetryl and ionization potential values of different donors using differences in energy value of tetryl and the corresponding anion [E_A^{Ad}] and that of different cations [I_D^{Ad}] and using Mulliken's theorem [E_A^V and I_D^V] and Koopman's theorem [E_A^V (Koop) and I_D^V (Koop)] considering both the complete transfer of electron ($G_1 = 4.13$)

Donor	λ_{max} of the complex (nm)	Ionization potential of donors (eV)			Electron affinity of tetryl (eV)					
		I_D^{Ad}	I_D^V	I_D^V (Koop)	Theoretical			Calculated from the experimental data		
					E_A^{Ad}	E_A^V	E_A^V (Koop)	E_A^{Ad}	E_A^V	E_A^V (Koop)
(considering $G_1 = 4.13$)										
IPA	517	9.252	7.212	6.322	2.033	5.128	3.359	2.957	1.553	0.599
EDA	516	8.708	7.092	6.058						
BAPA	519	7.619	6.614	5.555						
TEPA	519	7.347	6.613	5.681						

Table 3B. Comparison of electron affinity values of tetryl and ionization potential values of different donors using differences in energy value of tetryl and the corresponding anion [E_A^{Ad}] and that of different cations [I_D^{Ad}] and using Mulliken's theorem [E_A^V and I_D^V]; and Koopman's theorem [E_A^V (Koop) and I_D^V (Koop)] considering both the complete transfer of electron ($G_1 = 4.13$)

Donor	λ_{max} of the complex (nm)	Ionization potential of donors (eV)			Electron affinity of tetryl (eV)					
		I_D^{Ad}	I_D^V	I_D^V (Koop)	Theoretical			Calculated from the experimental data		
					E_A^{Ad}	E_A^V	E_A^V (Koop)	E_A^{Ad}	E_A^V	E_A^V (Koop)
(considering $G_1 = 4.13$)										
IPA	446	9.252	7.212	6.322	2.033	5.128	3.359	2.766	1.360	0.404
EDA	447	8.708	7.092	6.058						
BAPA	449	7.619	6.614	5.555						
TEPA	448	7.347	6.613	5.681						

Table 4. Comparison of the theoretical energy values [$(h\nu_{CT})_{theo}$] of the CT complexes utilizing DFT calculations with their corresponding experimental energy values [$(h\nu_{CT})_{exp}$]

Name of compound	Level of theory	Basis set	$[(h\nu_{CT})_{theo}]$ (eV)	Abs. peak (nm)	$[(h\nu_{CT})_{exp}]$ (eV)	Abs. peak (nm)	$[(h\nu_{CT})_{exp}]$ (eV)
IPA + TET	TD-B3LYP	6-311G (d,p)	2.962	517	2.399	446	2.782
EDA + TET	TD-B3LYP	6-311G (d,p)	2.699	516	2.404	447	2.776
BAPA + TET	TD-B3LYP	6-311G (d,p)	2.196	519	2.390	449	2.763
TEPA + TET	TD-B3LYP	6-311G (d,p)	2.322	519	2.390	448	2.769

and hydrogen bonding; G_1 is the energy of the “dative” structure of the complex corresponding to the complete transfer of one electron from donor to the acceptor. G_1 is mainly the electrostatic energy of attraction between D^+ and A^- and is equal to $e^2/4\pi\epsilon_0r = 4.13$ eV, taking the typical D-A distance 3.5 Å as used by various workers in this field^{22,23,25}. The term C_2 is related to the resonance energy of interaction between the “no-bond” and the dative forms in the ground and excited states and is assumed to be constant for a given acceptor.

For the determination of E_A^V (the vertical electron affinity) of tetryl, the eq. (6) was rearranged to get the relation

$$2 I_D^V - hv_{CT} = 1/c_1 I_D^V (I_D^V - hv_{CT}) + \left(c_1 + \frac{c_2}{c_1} \right) \quad (8)$$

and a plot of $2 I_D^V - hv_{CT}$ against $I_D^V (I_D^V - hv_{CT})$ (I_D^V = vertical ionization potential) was made (Fig. 2). The

slope and the intercept gave $1/c_1$ and $\left(c_1 + \frac{c_2}{c_1} \right)$ from

which c_1 was found to be 7.087 eV, 5.683 eV, 4.730 eV respectively from adiabatic energy changes and vertical energy changes calculated as before. From Mulliken’s Theorem and Koopman’s Theorem, E_A^V came out to be 2.957 eV, 1.553 eV and 0.599 respectively.

In case of CT complexes the energy of transition ($h\nu_{CT}$) must be due to excitation and electron donation from the highest molecular orbital (HOMO) of donor to the lowest unoccupied (LUMO) of the acceptor. However, the energies $h\nu_{CT}$ of the complexes found experimentally agree reasonably with $h\nu_{CT}$ values obtained theoretically. Though there were considerable differences between the experimental and theoretical values, but the results (theoretical) are based on a number of approximations and pertaining to the gaseous state. Moreover, the complexes cannot be considered to be due to charge-transfer only but considerations like dipole-dipole, dispersion interactions must be considered to have a better insight regarding complex formations. The results are presented in Table 4.

References

1. J. Rose, "Molecular Complexes", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1967.
2. R. Foster, "Organic Charge Transfer Complexes", Academic Press, New York, 1969, p. 303.
3. A. Szent-Gyorgyi, "Introduction to Sub-Molecular Biology", Academic Press, New York and London, 1960.
4. J. Nogrady and D. F. Weaver, "Medicinal Chemistry, A Molecular and Bio-Chemical Approach", Oxford University Press, 3rd. ed., 2005, pp. 9-80.
5. R. Mondal (Karan) and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 347; *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1998, **205**, 69.
6. D. P. Ghosh, B. Guhaniyogi and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 221.
7. J. Gangopadhyaya and S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 2000, **214**, 169; 2001, **215**, 883.
8. D. K. Kuila and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 830.; 2010, **87**, 557; *J. Soln. Chem.*, 2012, **41**, 36.
9. K. Sharma and S. C. Lahiri, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2011, **79**, 1063; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **88**, 1273.
10. (a) S. P. Sharma and S. C. Lahiri, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2008, **70**, 144; (b) K. Sharma, S. P. Sharma and S. C. Lahiri, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2012, **92**, 212.
11. S. Bagchi (Chattaraj), K. Sharma, A. Chakraborty and S. C. Lahiri, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2012, **95**, 637.
12. K. K. Majumder and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 163; 1997, **74**, 378; 2000, **77**, 447.
13. T. Urbanski, "Chemistry and Technology of Explosives", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1990, Vols. I-IV (Reprinted).
14. J. M. F. Douse, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1982, **23**, 4414.
15. J. M. F. Douse and R. N. Smith, *J. Energetic Mater.*, 1986, **4**, 169.
16. (a) A. Dwivedy, D. B. Parihar, S. P. Sharma and K. K. Verma, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1967, **29**, 120; (b) D. B. Parihar, S. P. Sharma and K. K. Verma, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1967, **29**, 258; 1967, **31**, 120.
17. M. J. Frisch *et al.*, Gaussian 03, Revision E.01, Gaussian, Inc., Wallingford CT, 2004.
18. K. Raha, P. S. Makashir and (Mrs.) E. M. Kurian, *Propellants, Explosives, Pyrotechniques.*, 1991, **16**, 55.
19. H. A. Benesi, J. H. Hildebrand, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2703.

20. (a) J. V. Janovski, *L. Erd. Ber.*, 1886, **19**, 2156; (b) J. V. Janovski, *L. Erd. Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 971 (cited in Ref. [36]).
21. H. McConnell, J. S. Ham and J. R. Platt, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1953, **21**, 66.
22. R. S. Mulliken, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 811.
23. R. S. Mulliken, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, **56**, 801.
24. T. Koopman, *Physica*, 1934, **1**, 104.
25. (a) S. Bhattacharya, K. Ghosh, S. Banerjee and M. Banerjee, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2006, **64**, 47; (b) A. Saha and A. K. Mukherjee, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part 1*, 2005, **61**, 1263.